

Improving Situation Awareness and Self-Adaptation in Autonomous Wheelchair-Drone Systems through Floor Surface Anomaly Detection

Rosario Gaeta¹, Franca Corradini², Massimo De Santo³, Francesco Flammini⁴ and Hangli Ge⁵

Abstract—Autonomous wheelchair-drone systems represent a promising advancement in assistive mobility, enabling enhanced navigation in complex and dynamic environments. However, floor surface anomalies—such as uneven terrain, obstacles, and hazardous floor conditions—pose significant challenges to safe and efficient operation. This paper presents a novel approach improving situation awareness and self-adaptation by integrating floor surface-anomaly detection in autonomous wheelchair-drone systems. A specific architecture for situation-awareness is proposed, combining machine learning-based anomaly detection with adaptive motion planning, to enhance the system’s resilience and responsiveness. Experimental results in simulated scenarios using Yolo-based architecture on real-world datasets demonstrate improved anomaly detection performances compared to the state-of-the-art, reducing the risk of instability and improving user safety. Experiments show a mAP50 of 0.764 and a F1 of 0.742 using a YoloV11s architecture. The research presented in this paper has been developed within the European project named REXASI-PRO, which aims to develop trustworthy AI solutions to assist individuals with reduced mobility.

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous vehicle driving is nowadays a hot research topic in various domains, especially in military, industry, aviation and automotive [1]. Autonomous driving aims to alleviate or eliminate human intervention, reducing risks. This issue becomes even more important for wheelchair users, for

whom a self-driving wheelchair can greatly improve their quality of life [2].

The European project REXASI-PRO (RELIable & eXplAinable Swarm Intelligence for People with Reduced mObility)¹ aims to develop a novel engineering framework for *Autonomous Wheelchairs* (AWs) supported by flying drones. The purpose of the project is the design of novel trustworthy-by-construction solutions based on trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (AI) for social navigation of people with reduced mobility. Since AW failures can be life-threatening, a trustworthy sensing system is required to achieve adequate levels of safety [3]–[5].

Recent achievements in AI allowed to significantly improve AI performance in the recognition of objects and obstacles through object detection and segmentation techniques [6], [7]. Their integration in smart sensors brought out an increased capacity of detecting anomalies [8], [9]. *Unmanned Aerial Vehicles* (UAVs) can be used to monitor the state of the terrain [10], roads or pavements where the AW must pass. That is especially important since AWs can easily get stuck in potholes or deep/thick cracks [11]. It

¹Rosario Gaeta is with the Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Salerno, Via Giovanni Paolo II, 132, 84084 Fisciano SA, Italia rgaeta@unisa.it

²Franca Corradini is with the Dalle Molle Institute for Artificial Intelligence USI-SUPSI, University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland, Via la Santa, 1, 6962 Canton Ticino, Lugano, Switzerland franca.corradini@idsia.ch

³Massimo De Santo is with the Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Salerno, Via Giovanni Paolo II, 132, 84084 Fisciano SA, Italia desanto@unisa.it

⁴Francesco Flammini is with the Dalle Molle Institute for Artificial Intelligence USI-SUPSI, University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland, Via la Santa, 1, 6962 Canton Ticino, Lugano, Switzerland francesco.flammini@supsi.ch and with the Department of Mathematics and Computer Science Ulisse Dini, University of Florence, Viale Giovanni Battista Morgagni, 67/a, Florence, 50134, Tuscany, Italy francesco.flammini@unifi.it

⁵Hangli Ge is with the Interfaculty Initiative in Information Studies, The University of Tokyo, 7 Chome-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo City, Tokyo 113-8654, Japan, hanglige@g.ecc.u-tokyo.ac.jp

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Fig. 1: SAMAPE-K Feedback Loop Model.

is also important for the AW to recognize and adapt to new situations. Self-adaptation is achieved with a Managing System following the *Monitor, Analyse, Plan* and *Execute* over a shared *Knowledge* (MAPE-K) feedback loop model [5], [12]. In other words, the system must be always aware of the situation [13]. Indeed, *Situation Awareness* (SA) is

¹<https://rexasi-pro.spindexlabs.com/>

the cognitive capability of a (human or software) agent to understand what is happening in the environment to be able to make correct decisions and perform actions. SA is defined as “*the perception of the element in the environment, the comprehension of such element and the projection of their status in the future*” [14]. Although SA was initially developed for increasing awareness of human agents, modern *Computer Situation Awareness (CSA)* focuses in making *Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS)* better aware of the situation for improving their autonomy [15] [16].

We introduce the *Situation-Aware MAPE-K (SAMAPE-K)*, as shown in Figure 1, which maps the typical phases of SA into the MAPE-K model. The monitoring system senses data coming from the monitored system and environment. Both the *Sensing* and *Perception* phases are located in the *Monitor* component. The *Analyse* component performs the actual *Comprehension* of the current situation. The future evolution of current situation must also be analyzed. Such *Projection* is used at the planning stage for making decisions that will be executed through physical control of CPS actuators. Indeed, while *Perception* can be easily mapped into the *Monitor* component, and *Comprehension* is associated with the *Analyse* one, the *Projection* is shared between *Analyse* and *Plan* components. The proposed approach enables self-adaptation for the autonomous system by modifying the current goal, searching for more data, or changing the plan.

The main contributions of this paper are:

- 1) We design a *Situation-Aware Drone-Wheelchair Cyber-Physical-System (SADWCPS)*, as illustrated in Figure 2. Such system focuses on increasing the Implicit interaction (not requiring explicit commands from a user) between the user and the wheelchair-drone system;
- 2) We implement and validate the object detection component (colored in green in Figure 2) in the *Perception* layer in a specific case study. We consider an urban outdoor scenario with cracked and disconnected floor surfaces, improving detection performance compared to current state-of-the-art.

The remaining of this paper is structured as follows: section II describes related works; section III discusses the methodology proposed; in section IV, the results of the experimental phase are presented and discussed; section V concludes the work and provides some hints about future developments.

II. RELATED WORKS

For the related works, we focus on two aspects: 1) we discuss the literature about SA applied to autonomous driving; 2) we summarize existing research about identification of floor surfaces disconnection in outdoor scenarios, which is the case-study we address in this paper.

A. Situation Awareness to Support Autonomous Driving

Most of the papers related to SA for autonomous driving focused on the development of human-machine-interfaces (HMIs), aiming to keep the human-in-the-loop.

Granillo et al. [17] made a review on such HMIs for electric autonomous vehicles, proposing an architecture made of a Perception Layer, Decision Layer and an Action Layer. Such architecture did not take into account the importance of the projection phase for planning, while it focused much on the perception through feedback sensors. Zhu et al. [18] examined the impact of visual assistance and cognitive load on SA during takeover events in Level 3 autonomous driving, where drivers were permitted to engage in Non-Driving Related Tasks (NDRTs). Through a simulator, the authors explored how NDRTs influence drivers’ SA under various visual assistance conditions. Considering road disconnection, Arvanatis et al. [19] proposed a distributed, cooperative and rendering scheme for increasing the driver’s SA through the detection of potholes, Augmented Reality visualization and information sharing with other connected vehicles or road infrastructure. Ge et al. [20] proposed an accessible path-finding solution by modeling predefined indoor mobility semantics.

Considering SA in AWs, Ji et al. [2] used a camera and 8 range sensors to design a system that can find a safe path avoiding obstacles. The system could classify situations involving persons to prevent accidents at traffic intersections. However, their work did not propose a system aimed at keeping the agent in the loop and did not take into account the aspects needed to achieve SA, such as projecting the situation in the future. While the literature is focused on the improvement of human SA of the user’s of an autonomous driving systems, the development of CSA of autonomous vehicles is less dealt with. In comparison, the approach we propose in this paper focuses on the development of an autonomous wheelchair-drone system, where the intervention of the user, who might have limited or discontinuous driving and perception capabilities, is minimized.

B. UAV Road Risk Perception for Autonomous Driving

Although there are no relevant studies in the literature specifically addressing the detection of floor surface defects using swarm systems composed of AWs and drones, pavement distress detection has received considerable attention in the broader context of road maintenance. Road surface defects can damage vehicles and contribute to deteriorating traffic conditions. Consequently, the early identification of such problems through automatic *Machine Learning (ML)* approaches is increasingly being adopted to support timely and effective maintenance.

Zhu et al. [7] presented a novel dataset recorded by an UAV with high-resolution camera for cost-effective pavement distress detection on roadway. The collected dataset included cracks, potholes and repairs as defects and is supplied with three possible object-detection methods based on Deep learning. Of all the methods, YOLOv3 [21] [22] was identified as the best. In reference [6], Zhong et al. adopted the dataset from Zhu et al. [7], and proposed a novel deep neural network encoder-decoder architecture for pixel-wise pavement distress segmentation. Despite such approach showed improved performance, it imposed significant computational

and memory requirements, making real-time, on-board implementation on a drone challenging. In the context of an AW-drone framework, a more suitable alternative would involve implementing an object detection method directly on the drone. In addition, semantic segmentation is a complex task which typically requires more data than object detection, and that especially with low amounts of data it is prone to overfitting [23]. A novel dataset was proposed by Zheng et al. [24] for road damage segmentation. Images were collected by a multi-function detection vehicle through a camera with a top-down shooting view and six damage classes have been manually labeled from experts. The study investigated both convolution- and attention-based deep neural networks for pavement damage segmentation. Luis et al. shared in their work [25] a dataset recorded by UAV for pavement damage detection on roads and proposed a model based on YOLOv8. However, the approach was limited to potholes detection.

Among the studies reviewed, the approach proposed by Zhu et al. [7] appears to be the most compatible with our drone-AW framework. This method requires the ability to detect a wide range of pavement damage types. However, due to the hardware and computational limitations, we focus on damage detection and not segmentation. Since the publication of Zhu et al.'s work, newer versions of YOLO have been developed. Therefore, we explore different and possibly lighter models to enhance detection performance.

III. METHODOLOGY

This work presents a *Situation-Aware Drone-Wheelchair Cyber Physical System* to improve AW autonomy and safety. The physical layer of such system is composed by the AW, who has to reach the destination provided by the user, with the support of the UAV, usable to detect and avoid damaged floor surfaces. The cyber layer is composed by a set of modules implementing the wheelchair CSA. The integrity of such modules must be checked by a supervisor. In Figure 2, the general architecture of such system is illustrated, highlighting the three phases of the Endsley SA model [14], *Perception*, *Comprehension* and *Projection*. In the following subsections, we will describe the modules of such layer.

A. Sensors

The SADWCPS must be equipped with sensors necessary to make the wheelchair autonomous. The wheelchair can be equipped with RGB cameras to perceive, detect and track obstacles and to recognize dangers in the environment, deep-cameras or LiDARs in order to perceive distance, and time-of-flight sensors. APIs can be used to capture contextual data such as weather. The wheelchair and the drone must be find in the space using Inertial Measurement Units (IMU) and Global Positioning Systems (GPS).

B. Sensing

The *Sensing* module deals with processing data acquired from sensors, which normally undergo cleaning or imputation operations to raise data quality, also reconstructing any missing data [8]. Sensor data fusion and merging is also performed in order to have more accurate information.

C. Knowledge Base

The data coming from the sensing phase are stored in the *Knowledge Base* modules, including the historical data that are acquired and cleaned. In addition, the user's goals are also modeled, together with decisions and systems requirements and tasks, using Goal-Directed-Task-Analysis (GDTA) [26]. The goals that guide the user influence the comprehension and planning phases. The relationship between the goals, tasks, and services to be triggered can be modeled by ontologies [27].

D. Perception

The *Perception* is the first phase of the Endsley SA model and consists of the data processing after the *Sensing* phase. The drone-wheelchair system must perform two tasks: the detection of potential obstacles and the localization of the wheelchair in the space. People, cars, and other fixed or moving obstacles, must be detected. In addition to a camera mounted on the wheelchair, the drone's aerial view is useful to detect disconnected floor surfaces. These detection operations require dedicated AI models, possibly capable of being executed on the drone itself. Solutions based on recent versions of Yolo [21], especially in their lightweight and mobile versions, enable fast and reliable detection [28]. At the same time, there is a need to locate the AW in space through the combination of IMU information, with GPS (outdoor) or radiolocation (indoor) information. Data fusion systems such as Bayesian networks [4] or Kalman filters can be used for that purpose. Here we focus on the implementation of the object detection module within the *Perception* phase, colored in green in Figure 2, to acquire the information necessary for the *Comprehension* phase.

E. Comprehension

In the *Comprehension* phase, the information coming from the *Perception* are used to build a *Mapping* of the obstacles around the wheelchair. Indeed, the map of the area in which to move can be taken from the *Knowledge Base*, coming from a previously built map or acquired through API, and it is integrated with the obstacles coming from the object detection, with the position of the wheelchair coming from the localization module. In the *Risk Situation Detection* module the information coming from the *Perception* and *Mapping* are further processed. In this phase, we assess the danger level of possible obstacles that have been detected to understand which risk situations are occurring. Classification or regression tasks can be performed with traditional or neural network-based modules to assign a class or numerical value of severity to the detected risks [29].

F. Projection

In the *Projection* phase, the system must be able to understand the future state of identified situations and assessing the potential consequences of its actions on future situations and, based on this prediction, select the optimal strategy. For this projections, ML, deep-learning, Hidden Markov Models (HMM), or cognitive maps can be used [8].

Fig. 2: Situation-Aware Drone-Wheelchair Cyber-Physical System Architecture.

G. Planner and Controller

The last two modules are the *Planner* and the *Controller*. The first uses the actual goals of the user, the map and the obstacle detected to determine a possible path in the map, then such planning is used by the controller that gives the real input to the wheelchair.

The interaction between the wheelchair and the drone is reported in Figure 3, where the UAV detects floor surface anomalies, sending their positions and classes to the wheelchair on-board computer, which is able to understand the severity of such anomalies, their evolution, and take appropriate decisions accordingly.

Fig. 3: Wheelchair-Drone Interaction View.

IV. RESULTS

The case-study we address is aimed at the implementation of object detection within the perception module. We focus on a scenario in which the wheelchair has to move in a urban outdoor environment and has to avoid a series of floor surfaces potholes and disconnections. Starting from the dataset released by Zhu et al. [7], we propose a Yolo-based object detection solution capable of improving the results compared to the state-of-the-art.

A. Dataset

The dataset we used is the UAPD proposed by Zhu et al. [7]. The dataset contains a total of 3151 valid images of dimension 512x512, in which six types of floor surfaces distress are labeled, in particular 1327 *Transverse Crack* (TC), 1340 *Longitudinal Crack* (LC), 414 *Alligator Crack* (AC), 173 *Oblique Crack* (OC), 94 *Pothole*, and 1622 *Repair*. Linear cracks, including longitudinal and transverse cracks are the most common classes. It is worth mentioning that oblique cracks are defined as cracks that are at a 30–60° angle from the direction of traffic. The images has been acquired with a flight altitude of 30 m and a flight speed of 5 m/s.

B. Metrics

The metrics we used for our experimentation are the classic Precision (P), Recall (R), and F1-Score (F1). For the multiclass setting, we adopted their macro-averaged versions, computed by calculating the metrics independently for each class and then averaging across all classes.

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}, R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}, F_1 = 2 \cdot \frac{P \cdot R}{P + R} \quad (1)$$

where TP are True Positives, FP are False Positives, and FN are False Negatives.

The mAP50 is calculated as:

$$mAP50 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N AP_i^{IoU=0.50} \quad (2)$$

while the mAP50-95 is the mAP averaged over IoU thresholds from 50with AP being the Average Precision, which is the approximation of the area under the PR curve, and the Intersection over Union (IoU), which indicates the overlap between the predicted and ground-truth bounding box. We also report the Frames per Second (FPS) of the model, indicating how many images per sec the process can execute.

C. Experimental Phase

We performed our experimental phase training and testing on a machine with an NVIDIA RTX A6000 and a CPU i9 of 13th generation. We compare our model against the object detector YoloV3 applied to the dataset released in Zhu et al. [7]. We compare such YoloV3 version against YoloV8, which has become greatly employed by the literature in recent years in various domain, establishing itself as the state of the art in this area [28] and also against the most recent YoloV11. In this paper, we focus on the experimentation on the lightest Yolo family of approaches, precisely on the tiny, nano and small models of each version. This is motivated by the limited resources of the UAV for the detection of the floor surface disconnection in real-time. Indeed, the Yolo family has been chosen for its well-known balance of speed and accuracy, enabling rapid and reliable identification of objects [11]. Yolo is a single-shot detector optimal for real-time application, since it was explicitly designed to be very fast compared to other methods which analyze the image multiple times (such as R-CNN and Fast R-CNN) [21]. The authors of the dataset [7] assert that the model does not need augmentation because they have enough data II. However, for our paper, we decided to do such augmentation understanding if it actually has or not significant effect on the performance of our model. In particular, using the ultralytics data augmentation, we have set an HSV random fluctuation in color, with 0.03 hue, 0.7 saturation and 0.3 value, a random translation of 0.3 intensity, a random scale of 0.2 intensity, a random vertical flip with probability 0.3 and horizontal flip of 0.4, a mosaic augmentation with probability 0.7 and a mixup with 0.2.

TABLE I: Comparison between the detection approaches

Models	Par	Metrics					
		P	R	F1	mAP50	mAP50-95	FPS
V3-Tiny No Aug	6.0M	0.589 (0.078)	0.401 (0.037)	0.476 (0.048)	0.493 (0.033)	0.290 (0.019)	555
V3-Tiny	6.0M	0.667 (0.041)	0.662 (0.047)	0.663 (0.030)	0.683 (0.030)	0.405 (0.022)	555
V3	62.0M	0.775 (0.043)	0.686 (0.037)	0.728 (0.017)	0.741 (0.022)	0.487 (0.021)	94
V8n	3.2M	0.744 (0.035)	0.701 (0.039)	0.722 (0.018)	0.746 (0.019)	0.490 (0.024)	476
V8s	11.2M	0.771 (0.030)	0.716 (0.025)	0.742 (0.022)	0.760 (0.020)	0.502 (0.022)	370
V11n	4.4M	0.749 (0.025)	0.702 (0.039)	0.725 (0.023)	0.758 (0.026)	0.500 (0.024)	526
V11s	12.5M	0.761 (0.045)	0.723 (0.028)	0.742 (0.019)	0.764 (0.018)	0.506 (0.022)	333

The comparison between the various models has been done through a 10-fold-cross-validation on the dataset, calculating for each metric mean and std. The results of the experimentation are reported in table I, in the form *mean* (*std*). Since the work described in the paper [7] provided best results with YoloV3 without augmentation, we have

performed our experimentation using YoloV3-tiny with and without augmentation to understand if there are any improvements. The mAP50 in this case improves from 0.516 to 0.683 while the F1-Score from 0.451 and 0.664. Since we registered significant improvements using augmentation, the other models were trained only with augmentation. Since the authors of paper [7] used the standard size of YoloV3, we have also performed experiments with such size version. The best results in terms of performance have been registered with V11s, which have the highest mAP50 and mAP50-95 values, respectively 0.764 and 0.506, and also an F1-Score of 0.742 and a Recall of 0.723. The best Precision, considering also the std, is the V8s model's one with a value of 0.771, but since we are interested in a model with higher recall, the V11s remains the best. Indeed, if a model has high recall it means that it has low FN, which is fundamental in our domain. V11 also has good performance in detection speed, with 333 FPS.

TABLE II: V11s by class: P, R, F1, mAP50, and mAP50-95.

Class	P	R	F1	mAP50	mAP50-95
Total	0.761 (0.045)	0.723 (0.028)	0.742 (0.019)	0.764 (0.018)	0.506 (0.022)
Alligator crack	0.740 (0.060)	0.663 (0.078)	0.700 (0.061)	0.730 (0.050)	0.491 (0.053)
Longitudinal crack	0.738 (0.047)	0.742 (0.029)	0.740 (0.028)	0.759 (0.035)	0.432 (0.024)
Oblique crack	0.598 (0.140)	0.573 (0.133)	0.585 (0.115)	0.583 (0.125)	0.400 (0.107)
Pothole	0.887 (0.102)	0.739 (0.115)	0.807 (0.077)	0.832 (0.077)	0.513 (0.077)
Repair	0.803 (0.050)	0.836 (0.035)	0.819 (0.026)	0.856 (0.027)	0.690 (0.034)
Transverse crack	0.803 (0.037)	0.784 (0.032)	0.793 (0.015)	0.826 (0.024)	0.512 (0.016)

In table II, the metrics for each class are summarized. The best performances are obtained for the class *repair*, which can cause discomfort in mobility due to slopes and uneven ground. The performance for the pothole have a mAP50 of 0.832 and an F1 of 0.807. The class with worst performance is the *oblique crack* one, with a mAP50 of 0.583 and an F1 of 0.585: realistically, the amount of data does not allow to distinguish well the orientation characteristics of the cracks.

The choice of the model to be used on the drone depends on the GPU mounted on the UAV, which is related to cost-benefit analyses that are outside the scope of this work.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We propose the novel SADWCPS approach for the support of self-driving wheelchair-drone systems. The approach is based on the Endsley model for SA to support risk avoidance in path planning. The case-study concerns the operation of the AW in an urban environment, where the object detection module of the SA perception stage is implemented using Yolo. Using the UAPD Dataset, the proposed Yolo-based approach improves the results compared to the state-of-the-art in literature, which ensures more accurate object

detection. However, to comprehensively evaluate the proposed approach, the whole system must be extensively tested, which was not in the scope of this work. Future developments will focus on extending the implementation and assessing it through experiments performed in city environment simulators. We plan to implement a comprehension module for the severity assessment of the cracks and floor damages. Results achieved in this research can be transferred to other domains of self-driving vehicles as well as extended to the general context of trustworthy autonomous systems [30].

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